

COMMUNICATION, INTERACTION AND MANAGEMENT IN A CLASSROOM

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Abstract: *This article deals with the main activities such as communication, interaction and management in a classroom effective education refers to the degree to which schools are successful in accomplishing their educational objectives. This definition concentrates on the responsibility of the teacher and relates the use of classroom management strategies to multiple learning goals for students. Following this definition, effective classroom management skills seem to focus on preventive rather than reactive classroom management procedures. It is increasingly characterized by student-centered approaches to learning as opposed to teacher-centered, with a large emphasis on students' metacognitive skills and cooperative learning.*

Key words: *interaction, communication, management, strategy, education, approach, metacognitive skills, cooperative learning, efficient, involvement, motivation, grouping, forming, arranging and rearranging, reforming, grading, school curriculum.*

INTRODUCTION. During the years of independence deep structural and substantial reforms and transformations in the system of higher education has taken place in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Main purpose of these reforms was to provide the adequate place of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the world community. Indeed, it was impossible to provide the independent economy, social and political stability, and development of intellectual and spiritual potential of the nation without rebuilding the system of education and upbringing. The state policy in the field of education that could transform it into the priority sphere has been developed and conducted.

Today there is no need to prove that the 21st century is commonly acknowledged to be the century of globalization and vanishing borders, the century of information and communication technologies and the Internet, the century of ever growing competition worldwide and in the global market.

Classroom management and the teacher

Effective education refers to the degree to which schools are successful in accomplishing their educational objectives. The findings of numerous studies have shown that teachers play a key role in shaping effective education. The differences in achievement between students who spend a year in a class with a highly effective teacher as opposed to a highly ineffective teacher are startling. Researchers define classroom management as "the actions teachers take to create an environment that supports and facilitates both academic and social-emotional learning". This definition concentrates on the responsibility of the teacher and relates the use of classroom management strategies to multiple learning goals for students. Following this definition, effective classroom management skills seem to focus on preventive rather than reactive classroom management procedures. An example of a widely used – and generally effective – preventive strategy among teachers in primary education is that classroom rules are negotiated instead of imposed. Teachers, however, also frequently use reactive strategies, whereas it is unclear whether these strategies effectively change student behavior. This may be caused by a lack of knowledge about the effectiveness of preventive strategies or by a lack of belief in their effectiveness. Teachers do not always believe in the effectiveness of particular strategies despite ample empirical evidence that the strategy has been implemented successfully in many. One example is that beginning teachers are generally advised to Effective classroom management strategies and classroom management programs for educational practice be as strict as possible in the first week of their internship and then slowly to become less authoritarian, whereas first establishing positive teacher-student relationships has been proven far more effective in regulating student behavior.

LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY.

Mastering effective classroom management skills is a basic competence for all teachers stresses that good teachers need to master a broad range of classroom management skills, and that teacher training programs should provide student teachers with a large “toolbox” of classroom management skills from which they can pick and apply particular strategies when necessary. Which strategies should at least be part of this so-called toolbox in current educational settings is still unclear. The reason for this is that the books that are used in teacher training programs generally refer to studies that were conducted decades ago or used anecdotal evidence rather than empirical evidence. However, daily practice in education has changed rapidly. It is increasingly characterized by student-centered approaches to learning as opposed to teacher-centered, with a large emphasis on students’ metacognitive skills and cooperative learning. Moreover, more and more technology is finding its way into classrooms, for

example, the use of interactive whiteboards, tablets, and laptops. These changes presumably have had a large impact on the demands placed on teachers' classroom management skills. Although, to the best of our knowledge, no studies have been conducted to explicitly compare the effectiveness of particular classroom management skills in more traditional versus more modern classrooms, an up-to-date overview of studies conducted in the last decade is expected to provide insight into which classroom management skills have been proven to be effective in modern classrooms.

Classroom management, as applied to teaching, involves everything that a teacher must do to carry out his/her teaching objectives. It includes preparation of plans and materials, structuring of activities into time blocks, direct teaching of skills and subject matter, grouping of pupils to provide for the most efficient use of teacher and pupil time, plans for transition periods-changing from one activity to another or from one place to another- pupil involvement and motivation, and adequate control of pupil behavior.

Taken together, classroom management can be expressed simply as the anticipation of possible problems.

According to Scrivener (2005), teachers are required to have "certain organizational skills and techniques" in managing multitude of tasks and situations that can occur at any time in the classroom. Teachers are also presented as leaders who influence their students, and who need self-confidence, self-respect, status, and a controlled professional life and classroom environment. Scrivener makes a very valid point when he says that teachers have to be able to look at and read classroom events as they occur and think of possible options.

The main areas of classroom management is the group of defined skills and techniques assists teachers in dealing effectively with a range of student behavior. Classroom management skills consist of rules and procedures that help run classrooms smoothly (Lemlech, 1999, p. x). It is vital that teachers establish effective classroom management strategies to use in their classrooms, so that children are keen on learning. A clear description of common classroom management areas is given by Scrivener (2005):

- Grouping and seating: Forming groupings. Arranging and rearranging seating. Deciding where you will stand or sit. Reforming class as a whole group after activities.
- Activities: Sequencing activities. Setting up activities. Giving instructions. Monitoring activities. Timing activities. Bringing activities to an end.
- Authority: Gathering and holding attention. Deciding who does what. Establishing or relinquishing authority as appropriate. Getting someone to do something.

- Critical moments: Starting the lesson. Dealing with unexpected problems. Maintaining appropriate discipline. Finishing the lesson.
- Tools and techniques: Using the board and other classroom equipment or aids. Using gestures to help clarity of instructions and explanations. Speaking clearly at an appropriate volume and speed. Use of silence. Grading complexity of language. Grading quantity of language.
- Working with people: Spreading your attention evenly and appropriately. Using intuition to gauge what students are feeling. Eliciting honest feedback from students.

DISCUSSION.

Some of these areas and various techniques for organizing and managing the class will be discussed in greater detail in the following subchapters.

Grouping and Seating - Changing the room's physical layout may make the classroom a more attractive place to study since it may also make cooperative work easier, revitalize fatigued students, reduce stress within the classroom and facilitate learning.

For each activity, teachers undertake in class, they should consider what grouping; seating and standing arrangements are most suitable. It is difficult for students and especially for young learners to sit still for a long time. It is essential to include activities that involve some movement. However, teachers should be aware of a constant movement every five minutes, which might be, for most students, uncomfortable.

Regarding the application of positive reinforcement, the research showed some improvement in managing discipline problems when random positive attention was implemented in the class. Although the findings of the track and the observation schedule comparison were not precise, in my opinion this research proved that a positive approach can lead to positive results. For more effective evaluation, however, I would recommend carrying out this action research in a larger class.

Conducting this action research enabled us to examine our own classroom practice and enrich our teaching skills. Moreover, it challenged us to continue working with various learners in the future.

Interaction and communication are at the heart of language learning and teaching; it involves learners in face-to-face or teacher-learners encounters in the classroom. Pair or group interaction provides a basis for language learning in general; it gives the learners practice in community and negotiation of meanings through taking turns, in addition to learning other features that are crucial in any interactive discourse such as how to initiate, respond and close conversations. The two dominant approaches to classroom interactions are interactionism and sociocultural theory. Both approaches emphasizes meaningful interaction among

individuals. While the formers emphasizes on language input and language as a means of exchanging information, the latter sees language as the greatest motivating force in human development and learning, the process of second-language teaching is grounded. Interaction takes place in a second language classroom determines what learning opportunities the learners get teachers, learners together are the contributing source in managing the classroom interaction and at the same time managing these learning opportunities.

Today communications plays such an essential part in the lives human beings. It is hard to think of a single activity that we engage in that does not involve communications in some way. In our busy world, we sometimes forget just how important communications are to our success, relationships, and, ultimately, happiness in life. However, indeed, communications does play a major role in achieving all of our goals.

Communication skills are essential for the successful future career of a student. In today's competitive world, communication skills in business are the most sought after quality of an educated person. Reading, writing and listening carefully are the three most important communication skills for students. These skills like most of the communication skills sounds too familiar as a result of that facts that we take them for granted. As regards reading and writing, the only thing that we need to tackle is to adapt with our growing age and concentration. With these two qualities, it is possible to develop reading, oral communication skills and writing skills. Apart from reading and writing presentations, reports and speeches are a part of school curriculum. This has been introduced in schools and colleges for the overall development of students. This makes expressive skills and managing skills also important for a student. It is also important to develop communication skills in relationships. What deserves more attention is that most of the students do not feel confident to make presentations and speeches. But realizing the importance of these skills in modern day life, most good schools have made it a regular part of their curriculum. Here comes the role of expressive skills and managing skills.

Expressive skills are used to express our feelings, thoughts and expressions and thus get across our point successfully to the listener. To develop expressive skills, students need to learn is how to communicate effectively and get the full attention of the listeners. After this, management is an important part of a student's life so development of management skills is also important for the success of the student. Listening skills are also an important skill that should be taught to a student. Listening skills should not only be limited to the classroom but also in a normal conversation. Students should be taught as how to give undivided attention to a person with whom a

conversation is taking place. Also, students should be taught as to how to show the other person respect when the other person is speaking. Such etiquette is a part of conversation in every sphere of life, be it professional or personal. Now that we have learned as to what specific communication skill a student must have, it is important to learn how to develop communication skills in a student. The first activity to develop communication skill in students is group activities. Teachers should limit group activities not only in the classroom but also ask students to complete assignments in equally divided groups. Also the teacher should continuously change the groups. This is so that there is more interaction among the students.

Teaching is, above all, a profession of communication. It is the teacher's responsibility to use **classroom management** to communicate ideas, content, instructions, feedback, and standards effectively to students. When teachers do this well, students are put in a position to succeed. However, sometimes teachers – myself included – inadvertently make communication errors within their **classroom management** plans that inevitably lead to gaps in student understanding.

RESULTS.

As a result of our research we outline some common flaws that can appear regarding teacher communication with students.

The first and most disastrous communication error is to not communicate at all. The teacher who fails to communicate is the teacher who puts students and other stakeholders in a position likely to produce frustration.

Often we make assumptions about what students know or can do while we communicate. We assume they understand what we are referring to; we assume they are listening; we assume this interests them. The more we understand the assumptions we make within our communication, the better we can account for those assumptions and make appropriate improvements to what we say.

Teachers can typically see the big picture in their heads, but it is difficult to transfer that same picture to all students. At times, teachers might communicate part of that picture effectively, but then leave other parts out. Incomplete communication will only give students part of the idea, but leave their learning and opportunities only partially fulfilled.

Most teachers have a particular style of communication that suits them. This is natural and appropriate; however, each teacher must also consider what forms of communication also best benefit their students. Relying on one strict style or mode of communication may inhibit all students from fully understanding what it is they need to know. Finally, we must remember that communication is a two-way street. While teachers often believe that it is their job to communicate *to* students, it is more

beneficial to think of their job as to communication *with* students. Communication involves listening as much as it involves speaking.

We can say grades themselves are a form of communication. However, by themselves grades communicate relatively little. Students can use grades as feedback to make improvements, but the more important part of a teacher's communication regarding student work comes from the written feedback. Since the grade is what is calculated and put into the student's academic record, it is far more tempting for the student and the teacher alike to put the bulk of emphasis on the grade rather than the feedback. The effective teacher will be the teacher who communicates the importance of the feedback over the raw grade outcome. How will you make sure students are looking at, understanding, and applying feedback for their growth? **Assuming students know the teacher cares:** Teachers cannot help but to care deeply about their students and their outcomes. Unfortunately, this is not a message students always hear loud and clear. It is important that teachers actively communicate that they do, in fact, care about each and every student. If teachers assume this has been communicated to students, then they run the risk of students never actually knowing about their teacher's care.

Teachers can communicate care through their words and tone. But their respect and responses to students are important, as is the way they use time and attention, genuine feelings, personal connections, and empathetic interactions to show they care. Gestures, deeds, and objects can all be used to demonstrate the care a teacher feels towards their students. Without these, students may not feel truly accepted or cared for in the classroom.

Sharing incomplete or insufficient information about homework: When we send students home with homework, we must make sure we have equipped them with sufficient explanation and support to successfully complete that work. If we share only part of the total picture needed for them to complete their work, then we are essentially setting students up for failure.

Once students begin work on their own, we must consider what resources and details they would need to comfortably complete that work, since we cannot physically be there with them. This communication requires an anticipation of student need and a full understanding of what we want students to demonstrate. If we communicate these expectations through a variety of means, then students will be more likely to catch the full picture of what they need to do.

CONCLUSION.

There is no doubt effective communication is essential to our task as teachers. The breakdown in our communication can lead to a breakdown in student success.

What are the shortcomings, assumptions, or ineffective methods of communication that you might be doing? Think more deeply about how you communicate, and your students will inevitably benefit from your improvements.

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